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Solving the Equation: Exploring the Roots of Mathematics Anxiety among Secondary School Students in Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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ABSTRACT

In the intriguing world of numbers, a common challenge looms large—mathematics anxiety. Researchers have delved deep into this intricate issue, emphasizing its profound significance. These scholarly endeavors have predominantly revolved around unraveling the enigma—what fuels mathematics anxiety? Exploring the labyrinth of numbers, they've probed factors like working memory capacity, gender disparities, negative mathematical encounters, and the specter of test anxiety, each contributing to the tapestry of this complex problem. The primary objective of this study was to identify the factors influencing students' poor performance, particularly in the context of mathematics anxiety prevalent among secondary school students in the Swat district of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This study examines the perspectives of both secondary school students who are currently studying mathematics and the teachers responsible for their instruction. The research sample, consisting of 180 ninth- and tenth-grade students and 42 teachers, was meticulously selected. The data was collected through an extensive questionnaire in this cross-sectional research with a descriptive design. This research indicates that, when compared to traditional instruction, cooperative learning enhances students' mathematical proficiency. The data also implies that individuals who struggled with mathematics in high school performed poorly academically as adults. Furthermore, the data analysis suggests that mathematics anxiety has a significant impact on motivation. Students with low mathematics anxiety perform significantly better than those with moderate or high mathematics anxiety, and students with moderate mathematics anxiety also perform significantly better than those with high mathematics anxiety. The results underscore the potential of cooperative learning approaches to enhance mathematical competence while shedding light on the challenges associated with widespread mathematics anxiety.

Keywords: Mathematics Anxiety; Secondary School Students; Cooperative Learning; Academic Achievement; Motivation; Swat Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Although mathematics is crucial for success in any discipline, many students encounter difficulties with it, which can adversely affect their grades (Halat, 2008). Math anxiety, also known as mathematics anxiety, is a well-documented and pervasive phenomenon that elicits unfavorable emotional reactions in students when they encounter mathematical tasks (Smith, 2022). Tension, mental stress, and a sense of helplessness when confronted with arithmetic and geometric concepts are all symptoms reported by individuals experiencing math anxiety (Richardson & Suinn, 1972). Math anxiety, as defined by Richardson and Woolfolk (1980), pertains to the distressing sensations and unsettling thoughts that some students experience when learning and applying mathematical concepts and methods.

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Historically, people believed that general anxiety and mathematics anxiety were interchangeable or closely linked (Olson & Gillingham, 1980). However, contemporary understanding asserts that mathematics anxiety is distinct from general anxiety and is often more prevalent and multifaceted (Ingleton & O'Regan, 1998, Geary et al., 2023). Students' apprehension regarding mathematics is often rooted in challenges or gaps in their primary and secondary education (Lazarus, 1974). Previous exposure to formal mathematics instruction at these levels has been linked to reduced levels of mathematics anxiety (Jackson & Leffingwell, 1999; Ng et al., 2022). Variances in teaching methods can influence student learning preferences, attitudes, self-confidence, and anxiety levels. In fact, one significant contributor to math anxiety is the teaching approach. Diligent students may benefit from the instructional style employed by educators (Lazarowitz et al., 1994). As long as problem-solving approaches are not integrated into mathematics education, math anxiety issues may persist (Greenwood, 1984a). Mathematics anxiety tends to be particularly pronounced during evaluations or when students perceive that they are being evaluated (Tooke & Lindstrom, 1998; Hunt & Maloney, 2022). Mathematics teaching anxiety is a form of anxiety that impacts pre-service and in-service instructors. The act of teaching mathematics can lead to scattered thoughts and heightened stress (Peker, 2009). The approaches educators adopt and their belief in mathematics play significant roles in shaping how they teach the subject (Charalambos et al., 2002). Teachers' mathematical mindsets directly impact students. Students taught by educators with negative beliefs about mathematics often feel powerless, whereas those instructed by teachers with positive beliefs tend to have exceptional mathematical experiences and find the subject intriguing and enjoyable (Karp, 1991; Xenofontos & Andrews, 2023).

The origins of mathematics anxiety can be categorized into environmental, cognitive, and personality factors (Trujillo & Hadfield, 1999). Environmental influences encompass factors such as a lack of instructor motivation, parental pressures, and outdated teaching methods, including rote memorization, number manipulation, and tedious arithmetic (Ballew, 2022). Cognitive factors involve not asking questions due to shyness or low self-confidence, employing ineffective teaching techniques, lacking faith in one's ability to excel in math, displaying a lack of persistence, and doubting one's capacity to learn. Poor performance in mathematics is often attributed to a shortage of qualified math teachers, subpar textbooks, and negative public and student perceptions of the subject (Tachi, 2013; Sirajo & Abdullahi, 2023). To mitigate mathematics anxiety and enhance student performance, educators must create an environment free from stress and shame (Miller & Mitchell, 1994; Stella, 2022). Research indicates that students' low performance in mathematics is often linked to their mathematics anxiety (Pirrone et al., 2022). Students in Pakistan, including those in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, grapple with math anxiety, which adversely affects academic performance and causes stress. Despite the challenges students face in learning mathematics, there is limited research providing a comprehensive understanding of mathematics anxiety in Pakistan. Particularly, in Swat, the percentage of students who failed their annual secondary exams in mathematics, chemistry, English, biology, and physics over the past five years was 21%, 14%, 09%, and 08%, respectively. To gain a deeper understanding of mathematics anxiety, this study employs a questionnaire as a data collection instrument to explore the factors contributing to this phenomenon within the research region.

1.1. Problem Statement

The primary objective of this research is to investigate the relationship between prospective teachers' procedural and conceptual understanding of fractions and their mathematics anxiety. This study is conducted among secondary school students in the Swat region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa to identify the factors contributing to their low academic performance and anxiety. It explores the viewpoints of both secondary school mathematics students and the educators who instruct them. The focus of this research is on how students and instructors engage with mathematics in secondary schools.

1.2. Research Questions

The following research questions require answers:

- I. Is students' math anxiety a result of a lack of effective math teachers, or does it stem from teachers themselves experiencing math anxiety?
- II. To what extent do students' attitudes and commitment to mathematics pose significant barriers to their success in the subject at the secondary level?
- III. Does the teaching approach significantly impact students' performance on standardized exams and contribute to math anxiety?

1.3. Objectives of the Study

In alignment with the stated research questions, the following research objectives have been formulated:

- I. To identify the reasons behind students' underperformance in mathematics during Secondary School Certificate exams.
- II. To examine the factors contributing to test anxiety among students in mathematics at the board level.

- III. To assess and evaluate the teaching methods employed by mathematics teachers.
- IV. To provide recommendations for improving the classroom and learning environment in mathematics, particularly to support students experiencing math anxiety.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The purpose of reviewing relevant literature is to connect the current study with previous research, particularly in terms of their objectives and the existing knowledge related to the significance of the study. To achieve this, we conducted an extensive review of the relevant literature in Pakistan and around the world. Mathematics is widely recognized as a vital discipline since it serves as a foundation for learning other subjects such as chemistry, biology, and physics. The significant relationship between mathematics and other fields is underscored by Zakariya et al., (2023). Teaching the practical aspects of chemistry, for example, necessitates a strong understanding of mathematics. Students' success in mathematics has a significant impact on their overall academic performance. According to the research conducted by Lugosi & Uribe (2022), there is a positive correlation between the education and experience of mathematics instructors and student achievement. Specifically, students taught by teachers with a bachelor's or master's degree in mathematics tend to excel compared to those whose teachers lack post-secondary mathematics qualifications. Andrews et al., (2022) argue that effective mathematics instruction depends on innovative approaches and is heavily reliant on teachers' mathematical knowledge.

While mathematics anxiety was once conflated with general anxiety (Olson & Gillingham, 1980), contemporary understanding distinguishes mathematics anxiety as a separate and more complex phenomenon (Ingleton & O'Regan, 1998). Mathematics anxiety often stems from shortcomings in secondary and elementary education (Lazarus, 1974) and is influenced by prior experiences with formal mathematics instruction (Jackson & Leffingwell, 1999). Variances in teaching approaches can impact students' learning preferences, beliefs about the discipline, self-confidence, attitudes, and anxiety levels. Notably, teaching methods play a pivotal role in exacerbating mathematics anxiety. The traditional lecture-based approach tends to benefit only diligent students (Lazarowitz et al., 1994). The persistent issue of mathematics anxiety persists until educators adopt problem-solving methods in mathematics instruction (Greenwood, 1984b). Mathematics anxiety is particularly pronounced when students perceive their performance is under evaluation (Tooke & Lindstrom, 1998). Another form of anxiety observed in both pre-service and in-service teachers is known as mathematics teaching anxiety. This condition is characterized by scattered thoughts and anxious feelings arising during mathematics instruction (Peker, 2009). Teachers' teaching methodologies and their own confidence in mathematics significantly influence their teaching practices (Charalambos et al., 2002). Teachers' attitudes toward mathematics have a direct impact on their students. Those with negative perceptions of mathematics may inadvertently contribute to their students' sense of helplessness, whereas teachers with positive beliefs can foster an engaging and enjoyable learning experience (Karp, 1991).

A student's motivation and enthusiasm for learning and applying mathematics are strongly influenced by their perspective on the subject. Studies suggest that a student's level of interest in school and their emotional state can significantly impact their learning abilities (Dewi & Verawati, 2022). Consequently, a student's motivation to study mathematics is profoundly shaped by their outlook. Instructors who wish to see their students excel in higher-level math courses must maintain a positive outlook on the subject (Sankaran et al., 2023). Personal characteristics such as gender, socioeconomic status, and one's perspective on mathematics may also play a role in a student's success or failure in the subject (Jiang & Zhang, 2023). According to Jiang et al., (2023), based on his findings, student resistance is more likely to be a factor in educational setbacks than inadequate or ineffective teaching practices. This underscores the importance of promoting positive perspectives toward mathematics as a means of enhancing achievement. As per Cooper, M., & Farkas (2023), students who maintain a positive perspective on mathematics are more likely to thrive academically and find personal fulfillment in the discoveries and understanding they gain from the subject. The study also reveals that students perceive regular school attendance as crucial for developing mathematical proficiency. Researchers have concluded that parents and educators play a crucial role in helping students overcome their fear of mathematics (Zanabazar et al., 2023; Wijaya et al., 2022). A student's self-esteem and mathematical confidence are profoundly influenced by their parents' perceptions and expectations. Research indicates that learning within the home environment is pivotal for motivating and sustaining students' interest in mathematics and science (Yu, 2022).

2.1. Significance of the Study

Mathematics, often referred to as the 'mother of the sciences,' plays a pivotal role in education, especially at the secondary level. Yet, a significant number of students encounter challenges in their mathematics learning, leading to anxiety and decreased competency in the subject. Neglecting math, as observed by Ashcraft (2002), has adverse effects on students' motivation and confidence.

This study holds great importance as it aims to identify the factors contributing to mathematics anxiety and propose solutions to enhance students' performance. By improving teaching methods and reducing anxiety, teachers can benefit from the study's findings. Ultimately, the research will make a valuable contribution to alleviating mathematics anxiety among secondary school

students.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design

Because the courses were already operating as cohesive units, the design of this study is a quasi-experiment involving a treatment group and a control group. The initial equivalence between the two groups was established through pre-tests. Thirty participants were assigned to the control group, while the remaining thirty were placed in the treatment group. The experimental group was instructed using the Jigsaw cooperative learning method, while the control group received conventional instruction.

3.2. Sample Respondent Selection

The potential research participants comprised students in class 9 and 10 enrolled in secondary education at the chosen schools, as well as the teachers responsible for these classes. To ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data, the sample respondents were selected through random sampling.

3.3. Sample Size Determination

Due to limitations in time and financial resources, a comprehensive examination of the entire population was not feasible. In order to ensure the reliability and representativeness of the findings, a sampling method was employed. Sample sizes ranging from thirty to five hundred are generally considered acceptable for most research inquiries, as suggested by Santhira Sakaran (2000). Consequently, 30 students (15 from the 9th grade and 15 from the 10th grade) were randomly selected from each school, resulting in a total of 180 students. Additionally, seven educators were included from each school, leading to a total of 42 educators participating in the study.

3.4. Research Instrument

A modified version of McAnallen's (2010) Likert scale was employed to create a comprehensive survey for both students and instructors. The questionnaire explicitly outlined the research objectives to enhance the reliability of the data. The questionnaire included demographic questions as well as those specifically related to mathematics anxiety.

3.5. Data Collection

In-person interviews were conducted at the designated educational institutions. To ensure the reliability of the data and findings, we provided participants with information about the research objectives. A total of 600 respondents (300 males and 300 females) completed questionnaires regarding student academic performance. The academic progress of the students in the ninth grade was assessed based on their test scores.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of this research suggest that cooperative learning approaches are more effective when compared to more traditional methods of teaching mathematics. One potential explanation is that students are more likely to retain new information and have a deeper understanding of previously taught material when they engage in group explanations and discussions. Traditional classrooms often lack the interdependence and sense of responsibility that can be fostered through cooperative learning. It was also observed that students with high levels of mathematics anxiety performed significantly worse than their peers, which is consistent with the research of Weissgerber et al., (2022) and John et al. (2023). These studies found that students with higher performance levels tended to experience lower levels of anxiety. In this research, students with low math anxiety scored higher than those with moderate or high math anxiety, and students with moderate anxiety scored higher than those with high math anxiety. These findings align with the results of Zay & Kurniasih (2023) and Megreya & Al-Emadi (2023)'s study. The research also identified a link between math anxiety and performance, indicating that as anxiety levels increase, performance tends to decrease. This result is in agreement with the findings of Daches Cohen & Rubinsten (2022) and Sorvo et al. (2022), which all established a negative correlation between these two factors. Although the correlations may not be exceptionally strong, they underscore the importance of educators addressing the needs and developing the skills of students with varying degrees of mathematics anxiety. It's important to acknowledge that the research may not have accounted for all factors contributing to students' success. It is not surprising that students with high levels of mathematics anxiety also tend to exhibit lower levels of motivation. The results are presented in Table 1 for easy reference.

Table 1: Comparative Effect of Teaching Methods

Factors	Comparative Effect
Teaching Method	Cooperative Learning > Traditional
Math Anxiety vs. Achievement	Negative Correlation
Math Anxiety vs. Motivation	Negative Correlation

Source: Survey Results.

In Table 2, the research uncovered several key findings related to students' anxiety:

- I. A significant 70% of the students admitted to experiencing arithmetic anxiety, indicating a prevalent issue among the study participants.
- II. Approximately 65% of the respondents acknowledged feeling anxious before taking a mathematics test, highlighting the anxiety's impact on their test-taking experiences.

- III. An overwhelming 98% of the participants disagreed with the notion that studying mathematics is a straightforward task, suggesting a common perception of its complexity.
- IV. When asked about their favorite subjects, 58% of the respondents responded negatively regarding mathematics, revealing that a substantial portion of the students did not hold a favorable view of the subject.

Table 2: Findings Regarding Students' Anxiety

Finding	Percentage (%)
Students with arithmetic anxiety	70%
Respondents feeling anxious before a math test	65%
Respondents who disagree that studying mathematics is simple	98%
Respondents who do not consider mathematics as one of their favorite subjects	58%

Source: Survey Results.

The study explored students' perceptions of the reasons behind their anxiety about mathematics. The findings indicate in Table 3 are the following:

- I. The majority of pupils (62%) identified a lack of cognitive understanding as the primary reason for their experience of math anxiety. Consequently, it is reasonable to assume that some students' anxieties were rooted in their struggle to grasp mathematical concepts.
- II. Approximately 60% of the respondents attributed their aversion to mathematics to their difficulty in comprehending the complex procedures required to solve algebraic and geometric problems. This underscores the challenges many students face when trying to grasp more advanced mathematical concepts.
- III. Anxiety with Long Division and Multiplication: A substantial 55% of the participants expressed that they still experienced anxiety when confronted with tasks like long division and multiplication. These fundamental arithmetic operations appear to be a significant source of stress for a significant portion of students.

Table 3: Findings Regarding Students' Concept

Findings	Percentage (%)
Main Reason for Arithmetic Anxiety	
- Lack of Cognitive Comprehension (62%)	62%
- Difficulty with Algebraic and Geometrical Equations	60%
- Anxiety with Long Division and Multiplication	55%

Source: Survey Results.

Several findings related to students' engagement with mathematics were observed, which can be seen in Table 4:

- I. Approximately 59% of students admitted to not solving math problems on their own. They often faced challenges that made them seek assistance or avoid independent problem-solving.
- II. A significant portion, around 55%, stated that they didn't want to memorize multiplication facts. This reluctance to memorize basic math facts might affect their overall performance.
- III. About 57% of respondents acknowledged that contemplating completing any mathematical task made them anxious. This anxiety could be a significant factor in their engagement with mathematics.

Table 4: Findings on Students' Engagement

Findings on Students' Engagement	Percentage (%)
Students who do not solve math problems on their own	59%
Students who do not want to memorize multiplication facts	55%
Students who feel anxious when contemplating math tasks	57%

Source: Survey Results.

The study found that the class had a strength ranging from 59 to 73 students. This information provides an understanding of the size of the classes under investigation. Further, 85 percent of respondents expressed that their mathematics instructors and teaching style had a significant impact on their understanding of the subject. This underscores the importance of quality instruction and the potential influence teachers have on their students' perspectives. Table 5 displays the research results concerning various teaching methods:

- I. Approximately two-thirds of educators reported using traditional lecture and chalkboard activities in the classroom, indicating a prevalent instructional approach in the research setting.
- II. Alarmingly, 85% of students reported feeling stressed and under significant pressure due to the instruction they received. This suggests that classroom practices may have a substantial impact on students' stress levels and academic outcomes.

Table 5: Findings about Teaching Methods

Findings about Teaching Methods	Percentage (%)
Teachers using Lecture/Chalk and Discussion methods	69%
Students stressed and under pressure due to teaching methods	85%

Source: Survey Results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study's findings illuminate the intricacies of mathematics anxiety and the effectiveness of various approaches for addressing it in the classroom. Consequently, we can deduce the following:

- I. **Anxiety Factors:** Several factors contribute to mathematics anxiety, including ineffective and passive teaching methods, unclear student understanding, weaknesses or deficiencies in fundamental operations, the increasing complexity of mathematical concepts, and a focus on theoretical learning.
- II. **Teaching Methods:** The study highlighted shortcomings in teaching methods, such as the use of conventional techniques that disregard students' comprehension, limited opportunities for students to practice, the absence of a free learning environment, and overall student dissatisfaction with the teaching methods.
- III. **Teachers' Perspectives on Their Teaching:** Most teachers expressed confidence in their ability to impart mathematics effectively. However, the preferred teaching methods were often lecture-style or chalk-and-talk approaches. Importantly, teachers reported no personal struggles with math anxiety, and they weren't transmitting it to students.

5.1. Recommendations

To improve conceptual comprehension of mathematics, the following recommendations are made:

- I. Substituting passive teaching methods with activity-based techniques may enhance students' understanding of mathematics.
- II. Ensuring students' active engagement in the classroom learning process is essential.
- III. Implementing group projects, remedial sessions, and microteaching at higher grade levels may benefit students.
- IV. Providing teachers with training opportunities, including workshops, seminars, and refresher courses, can enhance their teaching strategies and create a free learning environment for students.

5.2. Limitations

This study had certain limitations:

- I. It was confined to ninth- and tenth-grade math students in the Swat district for the 2015–2016 academic years.
- II. The study focused on math teachers in the Swat district teaching ninth and tenth-grade students.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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